

Women Auteurs Across Borders: Affective Resistance and the Decolonial Gaze in Dash and Al Ghanem's cinema

Chrysavi Papagianni

A few years ago, while working on Emirati cinema and on Nojoom Al Ghanem's *Hamama* (2010), I was struck by unexpected resonances with another film I had worked on in the past, namely *Daughters of the Dust* (1992) by African American director Julie Dash. Although separated by obvious geographic, temporal, cultural, and economic boundaries the two filmmakers adopt an affective lens, articulating a feminist aesthetic of care and proximity grounded in memory and tradition as well as on the feminization of history. Both works, as the paper argues, engage in affective storytelling, deploying visual aesthetics, embodiment, and memory, and inviting viewers not to watch but to feel the stories through camera work that emphasizes relationality and connection. The comparative approach looks at the intersections between affective aesthetics, creative agency, and feminist revisionism to explore how each film decolonizes the cinematic gaze through the rejection of hegemonic cinematic tropes and the foregrounding of marginalized histories. Drawing on their creative agency, I approach Dash and Al Ghanem as auteurs who share similar concerns. The approach is original and places Dash and Al Ghanem within broader conversations in world cinema,

providing a bridge that surpasses the dichotomizing East-West binary and allows for an intersectional, relational approach when it comes to understanding women's cinema.

Methodologically, I explore the sensuous proximity between the women in the film and their surrounding world, between viewing and experiencing. In short, between the represented and the intersubjective dimension of affectivity drawing on Affect Theory and Laura Mark's influential concept of 'haptic visuality' in *The Skin of the Film: Intercultural Cinema, Embodiment, And the Senses* (2000). *Daughters of the Dust* and *Hamama*, as I argue, are about experiencing, which, as Fuchs explains in "The Phenomenology of Affectivity" (2013, 1), is "regarded as resulting from the circular interaction between affective affordances in the environment and the subject's bodily resonance, be it in the form of sensations, postures, gestures, or movement tendencies." *Daughters of the Dust's* use of visual textures, slow pacing, and non-linear storytelling and *Hamama's* intimate framing and sensory immersion highlights this interaction, evoking an embodied emotional experience. Ultimately, the films reflect a cinematic paradigm shift, where memory, ritual, and storytelling become sites of resistance and renewal against colonization, be it mental or actual.

Daughters of the Dust is set in 1902 and focuses on the Peazant family, a Gullah and Geechee African American community residing on Ibo Landing, an island off the coast of Georgia and South Carolina. As the Peazants prepare to migrate north, they remain deeply connected to their African roots despite the intrusion of modernity. In this respect, the Peazants embody the broader experience of African American families shaped by ancestral traditions. The film foregrounds Nana, the Peazant matriarch, as a carrier of inherited rituals. Nana is framed as a mediator between the ancestral past and the transcultural present serving as a unifying force for the family. Overall, the film offers a nuanced portrayal of Black women's lives and histories that aligns with

postcolonial feminist efforts to deconstruct dominant paradigms and to articulate alternative histories.

Hamama also focuses on a female elder by the same name, Hamama, who embodies the tribal past of United Arab Emirates, its cultural rituals and its oral tradition. Like Nana, she is the counterforce to the encroaching modernity, a carrier of memory and wisdom that testifies to the past's ability to survive and 'migrate' into the future. Hamama thus emerges as the essential link between what once was and what now is, in a country where the Bedouin tent was replaced by 7-star hotels in less than two decades. Although *Hamama* is not as experimental and fragmented as *Daughters of the Dust* yet the film's compelling style cannot be ignored. Nor can one ignore the film's construction of a visual archive that reclaims women's contribution and counteracts stereotypes of Arab womanhood.

Both films have garnered critical attention with *Daughters* celebrated at the Annual Newark Black Film Festival in 1999 as one of the 50 most significant independent films ever made and acknowledged as one of the most influential Black films of the 20th century (Alexander, 232). Additionally, *Daughters* became, the first feature film by an African American woman to have a wide theatrical release. Similarly, *Hamama* won five international awards including Best Documentary Award from the Arab Film Festival in Sweden in 2011. This is noteworthy if we consider that the first full-length, feature film made by an Emirati filmmaker, Ali Al Abdul's *Abr Sabeel* (The Wayfarer), appeared in 1988 thus until recently there was hardly any infrastructure supporting cinema. Central in scholarly discussions is Dash's unique storytelling style emphasizing among other things cultural identity and historical memory. In the case of Al Ghanem, critics have highlighted her position as a pioneer Emirati filmmaker whose distinctive storytelling approach is informed by poetic sensibilities and a feminist rhetoric that blends "the aesthetic elegance of Emirati traditions with the expressive intensity of global cinema." ("Nujoom Al Ghanem," 2019).

Before proceeding with the discussion of the films, I provide a brief overview of the theoretical framework of the paper by looking at the theory of Affect that is gaining growing popularity in visual studies and which I use as a tool to contextualize the filmmakers decolonial vision and artistic agency.

The Affective Turn in Contemporary Visual Theory

The affective turn marks a significant shift in humanities and social sciences, emphasizing the role of emotion, sensation, and embodied experience in understanding visual culture. Moving beyond representational and semiotic frameworks, Affect theory examines how images operate on a visceral, pre-cognitive level, how they feel, rather than merely what they signifyⁱ. Affect theory has gained popularity across queer theory, feminist studies, film studies, and postcolonial theory, offering new critical tools for analyzing identity, resistance, and relationality. Foundational contributions by Silvan Tomkinsⁱⁱ, and subsequent developments by Gilles Deleuze, Brian Massumi, and Eve Kosofsky Sedgwick, have expanded its reachⁱⁱⁱ. Deleuze, for instance, emphasizes affect as bodily potential and cinematic temporality; Massumi locates affect beyond language and representation; Sedgwick underscores its transformative role within queer affective experience.

In cinema studies, the theory of Affect shifts analytical attention from narrative and cognition to sensory experience. Scholars including Vivian Sobchak, Steven Shaviro, and Laura U. Marks have explored how films engage viewers on a bodily level.^{iv} Sobchak, for example, employs a phenomenological lens to examine film as lived experience while Shaviro foregrounds affective intensities. Marks' notion of haptic visuality describes a tactile mode of seeing that implicates the viewer in an intimate sensory encounter. This framework proves especially useful for analyzing feminist, diasporic, and experimental filmmakers such as Julie Dash and Nujoom Al Ghanem, whose works engage with themes of displacement, memory, loss, and silence, outside conventional narrative structures.

Local Stories, Transnational Feminist Aesthetics in *Daughters of the Dust* and *Hamama*

Dash and Al Ghanem illuminate divergent yet parallel strategies of cultural survival by women whose histories have been shaped, and in many ways constrained, by the nation-state. *Daughters of the Dust* (1991) centers Gullah-Geechee women—descendants of enslaved Africans in the Sea Islands of the American South—especially Nana Peazant, as custodians of culture, using non-linear storytelling and spiritual imagery to resist dominant narratives of trauma and assert historical presence. The film reflects the experimental aesthetics and the non-linear storytelling of the Los Angeles School of Filmmakers of which Dash was a member. Described by Ntongela Masilela as the Black filmic avant-garde of the 1970s, the Los Angeles School of Filmmakers^v sought to develop alternative cinematic representations of Black life, foregrounding themes such as family, history, and folklore as is the case in *Daughters of the Dust*.

Since its release, the film has garnered sustained scholarly attention for its radical reimagining of African American identity and history, particularly from a Black feminist perspective. Scholars such as Toni Cade Bambara, Patricia Mellencamp, Jenniffer Machiorlati and Elena Machado Silva, to mention but a few, have highlighted the film's experimental aesthetics, feminist rhetoric and the construction of feminine spaces that reframe the legacy of slavery^{vi}. Overall, Dash's films, such as *Four Women* (1975), *Illusions* (1983), *Praise House* (1991), *Incognito* (1999), and *Rosa Parks* (2002), along with her short films and music videos, consistently engage with themes of cultural memory and history, while placing particular focus on Black women's lived experiences and viewpoints. For these women, survival has often meant preserving cultural identity against erasure by systems of racial capitalism and forced assimilation.

Nujoom Al Ghanem's *Hamama* (2010) also explores themes of female memory and cultural identity through the figure of an elderly healer

whose close connection with land, ritual, and oral tradition embodies a subtle yet potent resistance. Such themes keep recurring across her cinematic oeuvre with films such as, *Hamama, Sounds of the Sea* (2014), *Nearby Sky* (2014), and *Honey, Rain, and Dust* (2016) functioning as a counter-archive by foregrounding women's agency within a sociopolitical framework that often centers male authority. As Mandana Limbert notes^{vii}, Gulf modernization tends to valorize urban, male-dominated narratives, marginalizing rural and gendered epistemologies. Thus, Hamama reclaims female agency in the face of state-led modernization, economic shifts, and conservative legal frameworks that have historically rendered women invisible.

Although shaped by different national histories, namely African American and Emirati respectively, Dash and Al Ghanem converge in their commitment to centering women's voices through a poetics of affect and memory. In both *Daughters of the Dust* (1991) and *Hamama* (2010), they utilize cinematic form as a site of resistance, one that reclaims erased narratives, challenges patriarchal historiographies, and offers alternative modes of affective remembrance rooted in feminist and decolonial aesthetics. The fluid representations that build on affectivity underscore the interplay between individual vision and broader transnational dynamics, foregrounding their directorial agency and auteristic vision.

While the foundational premises of auteur theory are well established^{viii} and need not be reiterated here, recent scholarship^{ix} by Gerstner and Staiger (2003), Grant (2008), Jeong and Szaniawski (2016), Silver (2016), Hodsdon (2017), and Paszkiewicz (2018), attests to the theory's enduring relevance, especially in rethinking authorship beyond dominant industrial models. In this context, auteur theory remains a useful critical framework for analyzing feminist, diasporic, and postcolonial filmmaking, particularly in its capacity to situate women's cinema within a transnational context without resorting to essentialism.

Comparative attention to directorial styles across world cinemas can help construct transnational critical spaces that can transform, as Vertovec (2009) explains in 'Transnationalism,' "many kinds of social, cultural, economic and political relationships" (5). *Daughters of the Dust* and *Hamama* embody this kind of transnational consciousness. Despite their divergent geographies, namely the Gullah Sea Islands of the American South and the rural landscapes of the United Arab Emirates, both films reflect affective and authorial imprints shaped by specific local histories of gender, displacement, and memory. At the same time, they generate border-crossing identifications through their focus on women's agency, oral traditions, and visual poetics rooted in cultural preservation.

To put it differently, *Daughters* and *Hamama* align with other women-directed films that similarly resist dominant cinematic paradigms while invoking transnational feminist concerns. Thus, they operate within a cinematic tradition described by Hamid Naficy (2001) as "accented cinema," referring to works by diasporic or exilic filmmakers whose stylistic hybridity reflects complex cultural affiliations as they foregrounding the local, the intimate, and the historically suppressed. A prime example, here would be *In Her Footsteps* by Hiam Abbas (2012) which examines the erasure of Palestinian women's narratives within the broader framework of national displacement and patriarchal silencing. Abbas's revisiting of her mother's village becomes a ritual of reclamation underscored by slow pacing and intimate framing, allowing viewers to "feel" history.

Similarly, Kasi Lemmons' *Eve's Bayou* disrupts linear narrative and realist conventions to create a memory site through the eyes of a young black girl. Drawing on bell hooks' (1992) "oppositional gaze," the film privileges ancestral memory and spiritual subjectivity, framing Black femininity as a site of agency very much like Dash does in *Daughters*. Trinh T. Minh-ha's *Reassemblage* (1982), favours fragmentary, reflexive

techniques that interrogate the act of representation itself, paralleling Dash's non-linear, symbolically rich narration. Deepa Mehta's *Water* (2005), set in 1930s colonial India, foregrounds the plight and resilience of Hindu widows, drawing on historical trauma to critique patriarchal norms in ways that resonate with Al Ghanem's subtle interrogation of modernity and tradition.

The list of films is exhaustive, yet it is not within the scope of the current discussion. What is important to consider is that these films ultimately exemplify how women filmmakers often leverage affective aesthetics, memory, and non-linear temporality to reimagine cinematic language and storytelling. In doing so, they not only challenge patriarchal and colonial structures of representation but also contribute to a transnational feminist film discourse that privileges storytelling as a mode of cultural survival and resistance.

Cinematic Articulations of Female Agency in Dash and Al Ghanem

Dash and Al Ghanem, as we have seen, use cinema as a medium to foreground women's agency and recover historical memory, showing how cinema can serve as a vital site for articulating female resilience within contexts of displacement, marginalization, and national transformation. Both films discussed here, foreground elder women not merely as keepers of memory, but as active custodians of threatened epistemologies, whether rooted in the Gullah-Geechee traditions of the American South or the Bedouin heritage of the Gulf.

Hamama, the 92-year-old healer in Al Ghanem's film, resides in the modern United Arab Emirates yet her life is anchored in the ancestral knowledge and the Bedouin past. Similarly, Dash's *Daughters of the Dust* foregrounds Nana Peasant, an African American elder who represents cultural continuity for her family. The film shows the Peasants on the point of migration from Ibo Island to the North. As Dash explains in

Daughters of the Dust: The Making of an African American Woman's Film, Ibo Island symbolizes the Sea Islands, a historic area in North Carolina that is synonymous with Ellis Island for African Americans and thus “became the region with the strongest retention of African culture” (6). The film’s location, therefore, serves as a meaningful point of connection for many contemporary African Americans who trace their post-Africa ancestral roots to the Sea Islands.

In both films, the matriarchal figures emerge as living archives. To use Astrid Erll’s term, Nana and Hamama are “carriers of memory” and ancestral wisdom who “share in collective images and stories of the past, who practice mnemonic rituals, display an inherited habitus, and can rely on a gamut of explicit and implicit knowledge” (12). In *Daughters of the Dust*, Nana’s invocation, “We are two people in one body. The last of the old and the first of the new”, articulates her liminal role between past and future, tradition and transition. In the confrontation during the picnic, Nana opposes migration to the mainland which underscores a resistance to the assimilation and erasure of the Gullah culture.

In *Hamama*, the protagonist continues practicing ancestral healing despite her advanced age and the encroaching modernization symbolized by the image of the bulldozer lurking outside her house. Hamama embodies resistance and resilience not through direct confrontation but through ritual and proximity to the land. Time and again we see Hamama treating members of her community with herbal medicine, traveling long distances on foot, gathering plants and preparing remedies that draw on generations of Bedouin knowledge. These moments foreground her agency as well as her ‘rootedness’ and belonging. Her sharing of stories and wisdom while seated in natural settings, such as under the shade of a tree or beside a rock, underscores the role of the landscape as a backdrop for cultural transmission and the preservation of memory, where the environment becomes a silent witness to the continuity of tradition.

Hamama's resilience is evident in her ability to adapt to the challenges of the harsh desert life by deepening her bond with the land and by building an intimate knowledge of the landscape. She knows all her farm animals by name, which reflects a symbiotic relationship between the two, echoing what ecofeminist theorist Val Plumwood described in her *Environmental Culture: The Ecological Crisis of Reason* (2022), as an 'interspecies ethics' (184-188) where survival is fostered through interdependence rather than dominance over nature. It is this symbiotic relationship that helps Hamama survive in a present that bears no resemblance to the past. The respect she enjoys from the community that trusts her practices and comes to her for help despite the presence of educated doctors, or her choice to sleep on the traditional rug on the floor despite the comforts that global capitalism has brought in the country, shows her resilience. Her actions then represent cultural preservation and resistance against the erasure of traditional knowledge in the face of modernization which prioritizes development over tradition.^x

Nana and Hamama enact their identity through cooking, storytelling, prayer and movement that are inscribed on their bodies and landscapes. This reflects Judith Butler's theory of performativity, wherein identity is not fixed but instead it is constituted through repeated acts (1993, 32) and rituals that mirror the films' sense of rooted embodiment. This brings us to another important point, namely the spiritual dimension of space in the two films. For instance, Nana's burying the personal items on the island is an act that symbolizes the spiritual bond of the Peazants to the land and past. It also reflects the need to preserve the African and Gullah past in the form of a time capsule. In another scene, the Peazant family gathers on the beach to commemorate their ancestors and discuss the impending migration to the mainland. The family's sitting on the sand, surrounded by the sea and sky, underscores their deep-rooted connection to the land while the shoreline serves as a metaphor for transition into an unknown future. It becomes obvious then that the two films emphasize a bond with the land as a living repository of ancestral

traditions and wisdom that culminates in Nana's refusal to leave the island and Hamama's rejection of the modern way of life.

Dash's *Daughters of the Dust* reclaims African American womanhood outside the dominant cinematic grammar of trauma and subjugation as various critics have noted^{xi}. As Gourdine (2016) notes, "Dash revises the American cinematic archive, asserting African American women's historical visibility" (493). Dash's women reflect the diversity and richness of Black women's lives in scenes that show their strength and resilience. An eloquent example would be Eula, who despite confronting the trauma of rape she manages to transcend it. Overall, the focus on African women's ordinary stories and experiences represents a radical departure from dominant stereotypes.

Al Ghanem also reconstructs the stereotypical image of Arab women as silent, exotic or marginalized, propagated by orientalist tropes and patriarchal discourses. Without romanticizing the figure of the "authentic" Arab woman, she reframes Hamama's life story through tropes of feminine autonomy and resilience grounded in tradition. The film's focus on her daily routines and healing sessions serves as a visual cue to normality. Her interactions with her patients are characterized by assertiveness and a deep sense of responsibility. In one scene, Hamama persuades a male patient to show his injury, showcasing her authority and command over traditional healing practices, an act that resists gendered norms around authority in medicine. Hamama's active role in her community and her embodied knowledge offers a nuanced portrayal that challenges dominant stereotypes and affirms the vital contributions of Emirati women in the country's narrative.

The Visual Poetics of Feminine Resilience in *Daughters* and *Hamama*

In terms of cinematic language, it seems that both films build on poetic visuals and symbolic imagery, demonstrating an affective approach to visual storytelling through an evocative and fluid cinematic language.

Shifting between past and present, the personal and the collective, the real and the imaginary the films build on non-verbal affirmations of identity and resilience by emphasizing customs and the everyday life of African Americans and Emirati people. As Bambara (1999) explains, “Dash’s film rewrites Black women’s cinematic language, engaging with diasporic memory beyond linear time” (Bambara 1999, 87). Al Ghanem’s *Hamama* aligns productively with *Daughters of the Dust*, as it also crafts a sensory experience through a rich array of images, sounds, and colors that evokes a longing for the past while nurturing a sense of resilience that emerges through the quiet persistence and the deep-rooted connection of *Hamama* to the land.

The New York Times praised *Daughters* for its “spellbinding visual beauty” as well as its portrayal of the enduring spiritual strength of the generations of women who have safeguarded African culture (Holden 1992). The use of the term ‘spell binding’ points to the affective dimensions of the film made possible by Dash’s experimental cinematic language including for example fluid dissolves, close-ups, slow motion, and freeze frames among others. These techniques align with Gilles Deleuze’s conceptualization of affect in *Cinema II* (1989), according to which images are not recognized in the traditional sense but felt. In other words, affective aesthetics, as theorized by Deleuze, refer to images that bypass cognitive recognition and instead trigger visceral responses. In the case of *Daughters*, the result of the visually rich and emotionally impactful style adds to the film’s artistic and sensory depth.

The concept of haptic visuality, as articulated by Laura Marks, is useful here as it emphasizes a form of visual engagement that “muddies intersubjective boundaries” and is “predicated on closeness, rather than the distance that allows the beholder to imaginatively project onto the object” (Marks 2000, 162). This tactile approach to visuality fosters an intimate connection between the viewer and the film, encouraging an embodied experience of the narrative. As I have noted elsewhere (2021), Dash’s film is “imagistic” (275), as it ‘relies on a repertoire of images

that are emphatically portrayed with the help of a virtuoso camera that is not employed to register the here and now but to create visual links between the different spatio-temporal dimensions.” Through taste, sound, sight, and movement, *Daughters of the Dust* conveys the Peasant family's enduring connection to their cultural roots as a sensory experience.

Paula Massood in her book *Black City Cinema: African American Urban Experiences in Film* (2003), offers a critical analysis of Julie Dash's *Daughters of the Dust*, highlighting how the film constructs a distinctly feminist and Black lens through its innovative narrative techniques and thematic focus. One example would be the trope of the unborn child both that functions both as the narrator of the film and as a metaphysical presence that connects past, present and future. The film commences with the unborn child's narration, immediately establishing a non-linear temporal framework. Her voice introduces the Peasant family's ancestral ties and impending migration to the viewers, setting the tone for a story that oscillates between time periods. In another pivotal scene towards during the beach gathering, Mr. Snead, the family's photographer, prepares to capture a group portrait of the men. Through his camera's viewfinder, he sees a young girl with a striking blue ribbon standing among them. The grainy texture of the image, combined with the ethereal presence of the child, invites viewers to engage with the photograph on a sensory level. Thus, this unexpected appearance elicits a profound emotional response, allowing the audience to sense the weight of history and the palpable presence of the past.

The metaphysical presence of the Unborn child challenges reasoning and produces a Deleuzian affect through images that are not recognized in the traditional sense but instead they are felt. For example, during the women's picnic at the beach the child is depicted as a young girl, unseen but still felt by the other characters, moving among them, silently observing the women's activities—cooking, storytelling, and communal bonding. The interplay of light and shadow during these scenes,

combined with the ambient sounds of the sea, the soft focus and the fluid camera movements immerses viewers in a multisensory experience that transcends traditional visual engagement. This haptic approach which aligns with Marks's concept, draws viewers into the physical and emotional landscapes of the animate and the inanimate world of the film.

Similarly, if we look at Al Ghanem's *Hamama*, we will notice that the narrative offers viewers not just stories but emotional responses shaped by rhythm and ritual. *Hamama* employs an intimate framing that centers on the Emirati elder to create an experiential portrait through visual texture, rhythmic silences, and muted gestures influenced by her poetic background. For example, in scenes where Hamama cooks or concocts medicine the camera closes in affectionately on her hands that embody the past. In a pivotal scene where she touches the water falling on the plants, the extreme close-up on her hands and the water dripping, captured in slow motion, "elicits once again a sensory response from the audience" (Papagianni 2021, 222). The visual focus on the hand and water droplets emphasizes the sensory experience of touch and the significance of tending to living things. This scene's haptic quality engages the viewer's senses, evoking the feeling of water and the act of nurturing. It underscores themes of regeneration, sustenance, and the cyclical nature of life, resonating with the broader narrative of resilience and continuity.

The scene brings in mind a similar moment in Dash's film, when we see a close-up of indigo-stained hands holding Sea Island soil, allowing it to flow through the fingers like dust. At another instance, Nana gathers soil from the island, placing it into a leather pouch along with a strand of her deceased mother's hair with the camera. The visual lyricism of these scenes engages the viewer's senses, fostering a tactile connection to the characters' experiences and the broader themes of heritage and memory. All in all, the water and the soil represent a tangible connection to the land and ancestral heritage allowing the audience to "feel" the

history and embedded in the land and thus creating an embodied experience that transcends visual observation.

The above discussion has shown that Dash and Al Ghanem speak a shared visual language grounded on positioning women as custodians of African American and Emirati heritage respectively. The directors' virtuoso camera, as we have seen, intensifies the circulation of affect in the two films, moving viewers physically, emotionally, and psychologically and challenging them to rethink the power of images beyond what they represent. Al Ghanem and Dash's creative vision reinforces their status as auteurs who invite viewers to engage with the narrative on a sensory level, in sync with Marks' concept of haptic visuality. In *The Skin of the Film* (2000), Marks highlights that sensory, intercultural cinema offers a haptic mode of engagement creating a cinema of affect that resonates across diverse contexts. All in all, *Daughters of the Dust* and *Hamama* demonstrate how haptic visuality and affective engagement can transcend cultural and national boundaries to articulate a transnational feminist aesthetic that can become a means of decolonizing the gaze and conveying women's stories and experiences across the world.

NOTES

i. See for example, Fuchs & Koch in *Embodied affectivity: On moving and being moved* (2014), who emphasize the non-verbal and embodied dimensions of experience and situate emotion in the dynamic interaction between body and environment. In sync with theories of embodied cognition.

ii. Silvan Tomkins is often credited as the founder of affect theory having developed a framework for understanding emotions as biological responses that shape human experience in his groundbreaking 1962 *Affect Imagery Consciousness*.

iii. See Gilles Deleuze, *Cinema 1: The Movement-Image*, trans. Hugh Tomlinson and Barbara Habberjam (Minneapolis: University of Minnesota

Press, 1992), Brian Massumi, *Parables for the Virtual: Movement, Affect, Sensation* (Durham, NC: Duke University Press, 2002), Eve Kosofsky Sedgwick, *Touching Feeling: Affect, Pedagogy, Performativity* (Durham, NC: Duke University Press, 2003).

iv. Vivian Sobchack, *The Address of the Eye: A Phenomenology of Film Experience* (Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press, 1992), Steven Shaviro, *The Cinematic Body* (Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 1993), Laura U. Marks, *The Skin of the Film: Intercultural Cinema, Embodiment, and the Senses* (Durham, NC: Duke University Press, 2000).

v. Other representatives of the LA school are, among others, Charles Burnett, Haile Gerima, Ben Caldwell, and Alile Sharon Larkin.

vi. See Toni Cade Bambara, "Reading the Signs, Empowering the Eye: Daughters of the Dust and the Black Independent Cinema Movement," in *Black American Cinema*, ed. Manthia Diawara (New York: Routledge, 1993), 118–144; Patricia Mellencamp, "Daughters of the Dust: Dreaming in Motion," *Quarterly Review of Film and Video* 12, no. 3 (1990): 21–33; Jennifer Machiorlatti, "Diasporic Woman as Griot: History, Memory and Vision in Daughters of the Dust," *Quarterly Review of Film and Video* 18, no. 4 (2001): 395–404; Elena Machado Silva, "Re-imagining Feminine Spaces in Julie Dash's Daughters of the Dust," *Callaloo* 39, no. 1 (2016): 145–165.

vii. Mandana E. Limbert, *In the Time of Oil: Piety, Memory, and Social Life in an Omani Town* (Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press, 2010).

viii. Auteur theory's foundational premises were established by Francois Truffaut's 1954 "A Certain Tendency of the French Cinema," and expanded by Andrew Sarris' (1962) *Notes on the Auteur Theory*, who defined the director as the primary creator of the film and argued that a director's personal vision is central in defining both the form and content of a film, turning attention away from the studio system and thematic analysis to the director's controlling perspective.

ix. See David Gerstner and Janet Staiger, *Authorship and Film* (New York: Routledge, 2003). Barry Keith Grant, *Auteurs and Authorship: A Film Reader* (Malden, MA: Blackwell, 2008). Seung-hoon Jeong and Jeremi Szaniawski, *The Global Auteur: The Politics of Authorship in 21st Century Cinema* (New York: Bloomsbury Academic, 2016). Charles Silver, *An Auteurist History of Film* (New York: The Museum of Modern Art, 2016). Barrett Hodsdon, *The Elusive Auteur: The Question of Film Authorship throughout the Age of Cinema* (Jefferson, NC: McFarland, 2017).

x. For more details on the film's resistance to the discourses of modernity and global capitalism see my discussion in "The Salvation of Emirati Memory in Nujoom Alghanem's *Hamama*."

xi. See Mellencamp, "Making History: Julie Dash," 76; Bobo, *Black Women as Cultural Readers*; Hudson-Gibson, "The Ties That Bind," 43–67.

Works Cited

- Alexander, George. 2003. *Why We Make Movies. Black Women Talk about the Magic of Cinema*. New York: Broadway.
- Bambara, T. Cade. 1999. *Black women filmmakers and the narrative of history*. Durham: Duke University Press.
- Bobo, Jacqueline. 1995. *Black Women as Cultural Readers*. New York: Columbia University Press.
- Butler, Judith. 1993. *Bodies that matter: On the discursive limits of "sex"*. New York: Routledge.
- Clough, P. T., & Halley, Jean, eds. 2007. *The Affective Turn: Theorizing the Social*. Durham: Duke University Press.
- Caughie, John. 1981. *Theories of authorship*. New York: Routledge.
- Dash, Julie. 1992. *Daughters of the Dust: The Making of an African American Woman's Film*, edited by Julie Dash. New York: The New Press.
- Deleuze, Gilles. 1997. *Essays critical and clinical*. Translated by Daniel W. Smith & Michael A. Greco. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press.
- Deleuze, Gilles. 1992. *Cinema 1: The Movement-Image*. Translated by Hugh Tomlinson. London: Athlone.
- Deleuze, Gilles. 1985. *Cinema II: The time-image*. Translated by Hugh Tomlinson and Robert Galeta. London: Bloomsbury.

Deleuze, G., & Guattari, Felix. 2013. *A Thousand Plateaus*. London: Bloomsbury Academic.

Fuchs, Thomas. 2013. "The Phenomenology of Affectivity." In *Oxford Handbook of Philosophy and Psychiatry*, edited by K. W. M. Fulford et.al. Oxford University Press <https://doi.org/10.1093/OXFORDHB/9780199579563.013.0038>. Downloaded from https://www.academia.edu/21762316/The_Phenomenology_of_Affectivity

Fuchs, Thomas, and Sabine Koch. 2014. "Embodied affectivity: On moving and being moved." *Frontiers in Psychology* 5: Article 508. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2014.00508>

Gourdine, Dehanza. 2016. "The body politics in Daughters of the Dust: African American femininity in visual representation." *Black Camera* 8 (2): 493–506

Grant, Barry Keith, ed. (2008). *Auteurs and authorship: A film reader*. Hoboken: Wiley-Blackwell

Gerstner, David A., and Janet Staiger. 2003. *Authorship and film*. New York: Routledge.

Hubbard, Ben. 2014. "U.A.E. Filmmaker Seeks a Place for Women in Cinema." *The New York Times*, December 15, 2014. <https://www.nytimes.com/2014/12/16/world/middleeast/uae-filmmaker-seeks-a-place-for-women-in-cinema.html>.

Hudson-Gibson, Gloria J. 1998. "The Ties That Bind: Cinematic Representation by Black Women Filmmakers." In *Black Women Film & Video Artists*, edited by Jaqueline Bobo, 43–67. New York: Routledge.

- Jeong, Seung-hoon, and Jeremi Szaniawski. 2016. *The Global Auteur: The Politics of Authorship in 21st Century Cinema*. London: Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Hodsdon, Barret. 2017. *The elusive auteur: The question of film authorship throughout the age of cinema*. Jefferson, NC: McFarland.
- Limbort, Mandana. *In the Time of Oil: Piety, Memory, and Social Life in an Omani Town*. Stanford: Stanford University Press, 2010.
- Holden, Stephen. 1992. "Review/Film; 'Daughters of the Dust': The Demise of a Tradition." *The New York Times*, January 16, 1992. <https://www.nytimes.com/1992/01/16/movies/review-film-daughters-of-the-dust-the-demise-of-a-tradition.html>.
- Silva, Elena Machado. "Re-imagining Feminine Spaces in Julie Dash's *Daughters of the Dust*." *Callaloo* 39, no. 1 (2016): 145–165.
- Machiorlatti, Jennifer. "Diasporic Woman as Griot: History, Memory and Vision in *Daughters of the Dust*." *Quarterly Review of Film and Video* 18, no. 4 (2001): 395–404.
- Marks, Laura. 2000. *The Skin of the Film: Intercultural Cinema, Embodiment, and the Senses*. Durham, NC: Duke University Press.
- Massumi, Brian. 2002. *Parables for the Virtual: Movement, Affect, Sensation*. Durham, NC: Duke University Press.

- Mellencamp, Patricia. 1994. "Making History: Julie Dash." *Frontiers: A Journal of Women Studies* 15, no. 1: 76. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3346614>.
- Naficy, Hamid. *An Accented Cinema: Exilic and Diasporic Filmmaking*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press, 2001.
- Papagianni, Chrysavgi. 2018. "The Salvation of Emirati Memory in Nujoom Alghanem's Hamama." *Quarterly Review of Film and Video* 35 (4): 321–332. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10509208.2017.1422376>
- Papagianni, Chrysavgi. 2021. "Cine-things: the Revival of the Emirati Past in Nojoom Alghanem's Cinemascape." In *All Things Arabia: Arabian Identity and Material Culture*, Edited by Ileana Baird & Hulya Yagczioglu. Leiden: Brill. pp. 213-224 <https://brill.com/view/book/9789004435926/BP000017.xml>
- Paszkievicz, K. 2018. *Genre, authorship and contemporary women filmmakers*. Edinburgh University Press.
- Phu, T. and Brown, Elspeth, eds. 2014. Feeling photography, the affective turn, and the history of emotion. In *Feeling Photography*. 1–20. Durham: Duke University Press,
- Plumwood, Val. 2002. *Environmental culture: The ecological crisis of reason*. New York: Routledge
- Sarris, Andrew. 1962. "Notes on the Auteur Theory in 1962". In *Film Theory and Criticism: Introductory Readings*, edited by Leo Braudy & Marshall Cohen. (pp. 451-454). New York: Oxford University Press.

- Shaviro, Stephen. 1993. *The Cinematic Body*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press.
- Silver, Charles. 2016. *An auteurist history of film*. New York: Museum of Modern Art.
- Sobchack, C. Vivian. 1992. *The address of the eye: A phenomenology of film experience*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Sedgwick, E. Kosofsky. 2003. *Touching feeling: Affect, pedagogy, performativity*. Durham: Duke University Press.
- Tomkins, S. Silvan. (1962). *Affect, imagery, consciousness*: Vol. 1. The positive affects. Springer
- Truffaut, Francois. 1954. "A certain tendency of the French cinema. Cahiers du Cinéma". In *How to Read a Film: Multimedia Edition* (2000) edited by James Monaco. New York: OUP.
- Vertovec, Steven. 2009. *Transnationalism*. London, UK: Routledge.